

Fuller Theological Seminary

Luke 3:7-18

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By

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Introduction

Luke 3:7-18 contains some of the strongest language of repentance ever delivered in the NT, a message not often conducive with contemporary audiences yet offering the kind of straight talk needed to jar people from their complacency and apathy. Luke reports the multitude was going to be baptized by John and records his words about whether he was the Christ. His baptism was of water but Luke appears to be more interesting in his preaching than his baptism.¹ John tells his audience, "One is coming... who will baptize you with the Holy Spirit and fire," (3:16 NASB) a strange and intriguing statement. In this paper I plan to address the following questions regarding the text. What is the strategy and structure the author is using to communicate his point? What is the significance of OT passages in the text? What is the "about-ness" of the text and how can it be summarized?

Social Historical Context

John the Baptist is an embodied localization of Malachi's messenger of 3:1. Luke tells his readers that John, the son of Zacharias is across the Jordan in the wilderness (2:2) and is preaching a baptism of repentance for the forgiveness of sins. Luke makes explicit the connection of John to Isaiah, citing an evidently messianic passage (Isa. 40:3-5)², "The voice of the one crying in the wilderness." (Lk 3:4 NASB) Luke's precision is unique among the gospel writers when it comes to historical accuracy. David Jeffery wrote, "It is precisely 'the fifteenth year of the reign of Tiberius Caesar,' which, when correlated with Roman histories and that of Josephus, suggests that John enters upon the public stage in AD 29."³ Luke's reference to Isaiah 40 brings out the need for repentance for dispirited Israel at the time with a consoling tone of, "All flesh shall see the salvation of God." (Lk 3:6 NASB)⁴ According to historians John the Baptist came at a time when the nation of Israel was waning. Jeffery wrote, "Jerusalem was now again possessed by an alien power; all manner of vile judgment had fallen on it, and when the authentic voice of a prophet as of old was heard to cry out in the desert, many who were

¹ Bovon, Francois & Koester, Helmut & Thomas, M. *Luke 1: A Commentary on the Gospel of Luke 1:1-9:50*. (Augsburg Fortress Publishers, 2002), 122.

² Jeffrey, David Lyle. *Luke*. (Grand Rapids: Brazos Press. 2012), 112.

³ Ibid, 110.

⁴ Ibid, 112.

despondent but yet yearned in their hearts for the peace of Jerusalem went out to hear this prophet for themselves."⁵

Luke tells his readers the multitudes were going out to be baptized by John whose credentials are established in 1:5-23, 57-80). Luke used the infinitive aorist tense of **βαπτισθῆναι**, a verb meaning a ritual cleansing by immersion in water, literally to plunge. (BDAG) Yet, Luke highlights John's chastisement where he called them a "brood of vipers," and, "who warned you to flee the wrath to come?" demonstrating the seriousness of his audience who clearly did not come to be entertained.⁶ (3:7) In verse eight, John uses a play on words in Aramaic or Hebrew, an indication his audience was not primarily Greek, 'benayya' (children) and 'abnayya' (stones) indicating how God is able to **ἐγείραι**, "awaken from sleep" children, authentic offspring, from **λίθων τούτων**" from the ground.⁷ John promises verbal repentance will not do, nor will covenant lineage, but only fruit in keeping with repentance. **ποιήσατε οὖν καρπὸς ἄξιους τῆς μετανοίας** (Lk. 3:8 BGT) literally means "to make fruit worthy of conversion." (BDAG) How does John's exhortation for conversion and the baptism of the Holy Spirit tie together in Luke's gospel? How does the initiation of God to awaken stones from the ground manifest itself in the text?

The movement of the text appears to have a dual thrust, to bring forth good fruit and to cut down trees that do not bear fruit and burn them. The role of the Holy Spirit can also be seen as having a dual purpose, to cause healthy growth and acts of righteousness and to "burn up the chaff with unquenchable fire." (3:8-9, 18 NASB) Luke's theology of the Holy Spirit can be seen as the power to cause good works and the power to destroy worthless acts of unrighteousness. Luke introduces the idea of God's power, expressly attributed to the Holy Spirit, in verse eight with the word **δύναται** (Lk. 3:8 BGT), often translated as "able." And yet a power that is fleshed out in verse 17, "The shovel he uses to sift the wheat from the husks is in his hands. He will clean out his threshing area and bring the wheat into his barn. But will burn the husks with a fire that can't be put out." (3:17 CEB)

A soteriology of mutuality begins to emerge in Luke 3 where the Holy Spirit is responsible for new life and people respond in repentance, Bovon, Koester, and Thomas

⁵ Ibid, 113.

⁶ Ibid, 113.

⁷ Ibid, 113.

wrote, "Luke can only understand salvation as a relational association, in which, as in human love, the mutual participation of both partners is necessary. Hearts hard as stone must first become flesh, that is, become living (Ezek 36:26; this is why we have the verb **ἐγείραι** in v. 8)"⁸

Structure and Strategy

Luke primarily uses a dialogical structure in 10-14 to communicate his points. The egalitarian nature of the Holy Spirit can be deduced from Luke 3 as John the Baptist taught covenant lineage was not enough to avoid God's coming judgment, and the power of God is able to raise up from "these stones" children to Abraham, a picture of Gentile conversion originating from Ezekiel 36,⁹

I will take you from the nations and gather you from all the countries; then I will bring you to your land. I will sprinkle you with pure water and you will be clean from all your impurities. I will purify you from all your idols. I will give you a new heart, and I will put a new spirit within you. I will remove the heart of stone from your body and give you a heart of flesh. I will put my Spirit within you; I will take the initiative and you will obey my statutes and carefully observe my regulations. Then you will live in the land I gave to your fathers; you will be my people, and I will be your God. (Ek 36:24-28 ESV)

The progression of God's initiative in redemption cannot be clearer, and John's strategy may be inspired from these verses in Ezekiel. Obedience and repentance follow the actions of a firm and loving God to draw people out of complacency and disobedience to fruitful lives by the **δύναται** of the Holy Spirit. According to François Bovon, Luke saw the ethics of the Christian life coming from the wisdom of the Law and the prophets and can be seen in vv. 10-14 to avert judgment, and are highlighted at the end of Pentecost in Acts 2:37-47, as a natural progression and evidence of being filled with the Holy Spirit to benefit the community.¹⁰

The "About-ness" of the Text

There can be no doubt Luke teaches the Holy Spirit will cause division and judgment on some level. The wrath of God is made direct reference or alluded to in vv. 7, 9,16-17. Trent Butler wrote,

⁸ Bovon 2002, 123.

⁹ Ibid.

¹⁰ Bovon 2002, 124.

"John used a twofold agricultural image to explain Jesus' baptism with Spirit and fire. A farmer took a large fork-shaped shovel and tossed grain into the air. The heavy grain fell to the threshing floor to be gathered and prepared for use. The lighter chaff flew off in the breeze and had to be swept up and burned because it was useless. So Jesus' coming divided people into two camps: the people of the Spirit and the people destroyed and made useless by the fire."¹¹

However, not all believe John was talking about hell but instead was teaching on the discipline of Israel because they failed to live up to God's command to reach the nations. François Bovon wrote, "John's words of warning have become, by Luke's time, a sentence passed: the "wrath" is now inevitable, and others, the Gentiles, are taking the place of the children of Abraham. The unrepentant children have become like unfruitful trees for Luke."¹² And the Holy Spirit has a role in that sentence and execution. But how can this fire be good news as described in verse 18? It is good news in the sense that something new and unstoppable is coming, the old is passing away, and the fire of God is "unquenchable." (3:17) Justo L. Gonzalez wrote,

It is good news in the sense that a new reality is dawning. Thanks to the One whose coming John announces, evil and injustice will be undone. This is "good news to the people," because in Luke's usage, "the people" most often refers to the common folk, in contrast to those who rule over them and exploit them (see for instance Acts 2:47; 3:11–12; 4:1–3). But it is not good news for those who thrive on injustice, whose power is oppressive and unjust. For them, the good news is first of all the possibility—and the need—of what may well be a costly repentance.¹³

The Holy Spirit's Baptism and Fire

John would have been awaiting the messiah as God himself (Mal 3:1-4) and considers the "One more powerful" than he and his baptism for He will baptize with the Holy Spirit and fire. (3:16) In verse eight Luke uses **δύναται** to describe God's power yet in verse 16 he chooses **ισχυρότερός** which the CEB translates as powerful, a word that means stronger. But why did John couple the Holy Spirit and fire? Malachi 1:10, 3:2, and 4:1 speaks of God's purifying fire and sheds some light on 3:16-17 given how Jesus told

¹¹ Butler, Trent. *Holman New Testament Commentary - Luke*. (Nashville, TN: B&H Publishing Group, 2000), 57-58.

¹² Bovon, François. *Luke the Theologian: Fifty-Five Years of Research (1950-2005)*. (Vol. 2nd rev. ed. Waco, Tex: Baylor University, 2005) 122.

¹³ Gonzalez, Justo L. *Luke*. Vol. 1st ed. Belief, a Theological Commentary on the Bible. Louisville, Ky: Westminster John Knox Press, 2010), 52.

his disciples John is the Elijah of Malachi 4:5. (Mt 11:14) Bovon taught fire points ahead to the fire at Pentecost that fell on the apostles¹⁴, as evidence of the promised **δύναται** Jesus instructed his disciples to wait for in Jerusalem. (Acts 1:8) However Bovon also thought the Holy Spirit is involved in two aspects of incorporation of believers into the church, "Water baptism (as a visible sign of repentance, the forgiveness of sins, and appeal to the name of Jesus) and the laying on of hands (as an effective sign of the granting of the Holy Spirit)."¹⁵ Bovon also explained how fire is metaphorical of judgment in the Hebrew Bible and the unrepentant sinner falls prey to it, but Luke no longer appears to focus on eschatological judgment but looks ahead to the outpouring of the Holy Spirit given by Christ.¹⁶ Justo L. Gonzalez wrote, "John calls people to repent, and when they do this he baptizes them as a sign that they are cleansed of their former impurity. But Christian baptism, while still employing water, is "with the Holy Spirit and with fire." It is a cleansing (fire) and empowering (Holy Spirit)."¹⁷

Real Repentance as Evidence of Changed Hearts

The Baptist's image of an ax in verse 9 is ready to "lay bare" the roots and destroy by fire strikes deeply into his listener's hearts. This image would have taken aback a farmer who understood the process of removing a tree so that it has no chance of returning. Bovon wrote, "Deut 19:5 gives insight into the work of a lumberjack. Ps 74:6 uses the image of the ax for the work of the enemies, Jer 46:22 for the punishment of Egypt by the Assyrians. The connection of tree and fruit is common in Jewish parenesis; Jesus and the Christians will adopt it. Does not the axe and fire threaten every community and all believers who bear no fruit?"¹⁸

Luke identifies the crowd and the people and their responses to the stern message of coming judgment on the unrepentant. Bovon wrote, "The people addressed are "the crowds" (**ὄχλοι** vv. 7, 10) and "the people" (**λαοῦ**, vv. 15, 18)- these are probably synonymous." "What shall we do? **τί ποιήσωμεν**, repeated thrice (vv. 10, 12, 14) is also found in Acts 2:37 in response to Peter's message.¹⁹ Even though the questions have no

¹⁴ Bovon 2005, 248.

¹⁵ Ibid.

¹⁶ Ibid.

¹⁷ Gonzalez, 52.

¹⁸ Bovon 2002, 123.

¹⁹ Bovon 2002, 122.

overt economic implications, the answers by John are primarily economic,²⁰ in contrast to Acts 2:38, where Peter says "Repent and be baptized, every one of you, in the name of Jesus Christ for the forgiveness of your sins. And you will receive the gift of the Holy Spirit." (NIV)

The first command, v.11 is to the crowds, all Israel is told to share their clothing and food with the poor, an essential way of showing hospitality in the ancient world (Deut 15:4).²¹ John's exhortation to the soldiers and tax-collectors, to specifically demonstrate their repentance within their vocations, draws on Luke's theological point of reference that no one is excluded from repentance and salvation. The soldiers wanted to clarify if they too are included in the possibility of salvation and asked **καὶ ἡμεῖς**, "and we?", showing how much they desired to be part of God's redemptive plan. The socio-economic message of inclusion runs throughout the Third Gospel with God's reversal of status and position and a call for Christians to use their wealth to alleviate the hardships of the poor.²² The lowest of society are called and included in God's action.²³ However, the just use of power, money, and possessions is shown in Luke's attention to John's preaching here and is unique among the synoptic gospels.

In vv.15-18 Luke continues to utilize a dialogical structure to disclose the teaching and preaching of the Baptist. Luke turns the attention away from the wrath of God to the coming of the Christ by describing the hearts of the people and their state of expectation. Luke focuses on the place where humans ponder questions and make decisions-the heart, **ταῖς καρδίαις αὐτῶν** (Lk. 3:15 BGT), and sheds light on his inclination toward human responsibility and reason. Luke uniquely simplifies the question and answer to his identity, to whether or not John is the Christ, while John's gospel includes Elijah and The Prophet as possibilities, revealing Luke's conviction. (John 1:21)²⁴

Conclusion

The summary of the pericope of 3:7-18 is found in verse 18, a rather surprising statement by Luke. How can this warning of fire and judgment be considered

²⁰ Thomas E. Phillips *Reading Issues of Wealth and Poverty in Luke-Acts*. Studies in Bible & Early Christianity. (Lewiston: Edwin Mellen Press, 2000). 93.

²¹ Bovon 2002, 124.

²² Phillips 2000, 29.

²³ Bovon 2002, 124.

²⁴ Bovon 2002, 125.

εὐηγγελίζετο to the people? Good news is evident in the clarifying questions for inclusion by the tax collectors and soldiers who would have been considered outcasts and beyond redemption. And it is **εὐηγγελίζετο** by the question regarding John's identity as they are wondering whether he is the Christ, a tribute of respect and conviction. This wondering or pondering (**διελογίζετο**) is reminiscent of what Mary did when the angel told her she was favored. (Lk 1:29) Therefore, Luke asks his readers to ponder John's message of repentance, the questions posed to John and his answers, and to ponder the coming of Jesus and the kind of baptism he brings with the Holy Spirit and fire. It is good news because everyone can be included by repentance and faith.

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